

Making Research Data Findable with B2FIND

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B2FIND Overview

Search data

<http://b2find.eudat.eu/>

- simple and user-friendly **discovery portal** for **research data**, allows text- and faceted search **across scientific disciplines**
- up to now **62** repositories on productive machine, several more on test-instance; **>1 Mio metadata records of research datasets**
- enables findability of data stored in **EUDAT data centers**, other **research infrastructures** or **data providers**, covering divergent research areas
- was the central indexing tool for **EOSC-hub**; registered discovery service in **EOSC**, currently part of **DICE** project

Project Summary

Consortium: 24 Partners
Coordinator: CINECA

Grant Agreement: 101017207
Call: INFRAEOSC-07-2020

30 months
(1 Jan 2021 – 30 Jun 2023)

Enable a European storage and data management infrastructure for EOSC
Provide generic services to store, find, access, and process data in a consistent and persistent way

Budget: € 6.997.706,66

18 providers from 11 European countries are offering 14 state-of-the-art data management services together with more than 50 PB of storage capacity

- ▶ **14 services** covering the whole research data management lifecycle
- ▶ **>50 PB** of storage offered with the services
- ▶ Standard requests to be served within **2 weeks**
- ▶ Support can be provided for customised solutions
- ▶ Request the services from the EOSC marketplace [HERE](#)
- ▶ Ask for further information by email [HERE](#)

Data Discovery

Making research data findable
Data source harvestable and to make data widely discoverable

Data Repository

Long-term data resources preservation and sharing
To store non-active FAIR data

Policies based Data Archive

Mid-long term data resources, accessible from computing facilities to store non-active research data
Value-added services (integrity checks, replications, ...) for long-term, stable data archives.

Data Archive

Mid term storage resources after/between projects, Accessible from computing facilities to store non-active research data, bitwise preservation

Personal and/or Project workspace

Mid-term storage during project,
Good connection to computing facilities,
To store active resource data

Metadata Ingestion

supported channels

OAI – PMH
CSW
Rest API
[SparQL]

Harvesting

supported metadata

Dublin Core
Datacite
OpenAire
EUDAT Core
ISO 19139/19139, FGDC
community specific

Search

free text search
faceted search

e.g. spatial/temporal
coverage

narrow down results

Mapping

technical format conversion
semantic „readers“ for standards, mapping
to target schema; including
vocabularies, validation
specific according to community needs

B2FIND as Catalogue and Aggregator

Ingestion of Metadata

- from EUDAT's B2SHARE
- from research communities worldwide across all academic disciplines

Exposure of Metadata

- OAI-PMH extension for CKAN
- B2FIND is a metadata provider for OpenAIRE and EOSC

Useful B2FIND Features for Data Searchers

- * Search across disciplines in one easy-to-use portal
- * Easy access to source dataset (if openly accessible) and/or its original metadata
- * Filter options:
 - * spatial coverage (easily selectable on a map)
 - * temporal coverage
 - * measuring instrument, eg. beamline, float sensor
 - * search by research discipline

Useful B2FIND Features for Data Providers

DATA CATALOGUE

REPOSITORIES

COMMUNITIES

FOR PROVIDERS

FOR USERS

ABOUT

- * Possibility to display single repositories as well as overarching projects or research infrastructures („Communities“), e.g. PaNOSC
- * Could be used to display NFDi4ing as a Community, with belonging individual data repositories under its umbrella
- * Useful feature for creating Community-wide search spaces
- * Metadata record links back to original source and full metadata

Home / Communities / PaNOSC

PaNOSC

The PaNOSC project, Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud, brings together six strategic European research infrastructures (ESRF, CERIC-ERIC, ELI Delivery Consortium, the...)

[read more](#)

Followers: **0** | Datasets: **2.7k**

Spatial Coverage

Temporal Coverage

Publication Year

Repositories

Filter: 9-1

- ESRF **2332**
- ESS **456**
- CERIC **7**

Communities

Filter: 9-1

PaNOSC **2785**

Datasets About

Search datasets...

2,795 datasets found Order by: Relevance

Degradation of green historical pigment Verdigris

Preliminary study in order to establish the suitability of the instrumental method

2022_SciComPty_paper

Data and metadata used in a 2022 manuscript on the SciComPty ptychography software framework

manuscript_dataset_sample_prep_XRF2022

FAIR and Open dataset for the manuscript...

Crystallisation lab-Marta

20195588-2

PyPore3D

FAIR and Open data repository for the raw data of the manuscript : PyPore3D: An open source software tool for imaging data processing and analysis of porous and multiphase...

manuscript_dataset_for_Compressive_Sensing_for_Dynamic_XRF_Scanning

OpenFAIR Dataset of Synchrotron Low Energy XRF and STXM files used in a manuscript on "Compressive Sensing for Dynamic XRF Scanning" Synchrotron Low Energy XRF and STXM Dataset...

COVID-19 Multiscale Imaging of COVID-19 Lung Injury Patterns Bridges the Gap ...

This is an addition to Fast-track Proposal #20202210 (SISSIAFM), please process the proposals combined. COVID-19 related project in conjunction with structural lung...

Sample Data from V20

This data was collected as part of BrightnESS, funded by the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020, under grant...

Sample Data from V20

This data was collected as part of BrightnESS, funded by the European Union Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020, under grant...

Home / Communities / Nordic Archaeology

Nordic Archaeology

This Community consists of records from Danish and Norwegian Sites and Monuments Data Providers. Askeladden is a Norwegian database system for managing cultural heritage...

[read more](#)

Followers: **0** | Datasets: **398.1k**

Spatial Coverage

Temporal Coverage

Publication Year

Repositories

Filter: 9-1

- SLKS **206278**
- Askeladden **181636**

Communities

Filter: 9-1

Nordic Archaeology **398114**

Datasets About

Search datasets...

398,114 datasets found Order by: Relevance

130812-354 Viskum Høje

This record describes ancient sites and monuments as well archaeological excavations undertaken by Danish museums. Excerpt of the Danish description of events: Mulig del af jysk...

090702-2 Tante Dorthees have

This record describes ancient sites and monuments as well archaeological excavations undertaken by Danish museums. Excerpt of the Danish description of events: Skår af glaseret...

010510-57 Kassemose

This record describes ancient sites and monuments as well archaeological excavations undertaken by Danish museums. Excerpt of the Danish description of events: Fund af...

010510-56 Kassemose

This record describes ancient sites and monuments as well archaeological excavations undertaken by Danish museums. Excerpt of the Danish description of events: to...

090704-198 St. Rise

This record describes ancient sites and monuments as well archaeological excavations undertaken by Danish museums. Excerpt of the Danish description of events: Grube med skår af...

200103-271 Fuglebæk

This record describes ancient sites and monuments as well archaeological excavations undertaken by Danish museums. Excerpt of the Danish description of events: bjergartsekse,...

010109-218 Hyrdehøj

This record describes ancient sites and monuments as well archaeological excavations undertaken by Danish museums. Excerpt of the Danish description of events: Fund af tre...

160406-277 Addit

This record describes ancient sites and monuments as well archaeological excavations undertaken by Danish museums. Excerpt of the Danish description of events: 2020-03-05:...

Let's take a look!

* <https://b2find.eudat.eu>

* Do you have any questions?

JOIN OUR COMMUNITY

DICEosc

/company/diceosc

More Information

B2FIND

<https://b2find.eudat.eu>

B2FIND Guidelines for Data Providers

<https://b2find.eudat.eu/site/forproviders/>

B2FIND in GitHub

<https://github.com/EUDAT-B2FIND/md-ingestion>

Contact for Metadata Integration in B2FIND

DICE

<https://www.dice-eosc.eu/contact>

EUDAT RT

<https://eudat.eu/contact-support-request>